

ISTANBUL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY ★ GRADUATE SCHOOL

**OPTICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF COLLAGEN IN SOLUTION BY USING
DOUBLE INTEGRATING SPHERE SYSTEM**

M.Sc. THESIS

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Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering

Biomedical Engineering Programme

NOVEMBER 2021

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İSTANBUL TEKNİK ÜNİVERSİTESİ★ LİSANSÜSTÜ EĞİTİM ENSTİTÜSÜ

**ÇİFT TOPLAYICI KÜRE SİSTEMİ KULLANILARAK ÇÖZELTİDEKİ
KOLAJENİN OPTİK NİTELENDİRİLMESİ**

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To my husband and son,

FOREWORD

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ABBREVIATIONS

3D	: Three Dimensional
ABS	: Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene
g	: Gram
IAD	: Inverse adding-doubling
LLLT	: Low-level laser therapy
M	: Molar
ml	: Milliliter
mm	: Millimeter
MPa	: Megapascal
MR	: Normalized reflectance
MT	: Normalized transmittance
NIRS	: Near Infrared Spectrum
nm	: Nanometer
PBS	: Phosphate-buffered saline
PC	: Personal Computer
pH	: Power of hydrogen
PhD	: Doctor of Philosophy
R	: Reflectance
rpm	: Revolutions per minute
RTE	: Radiative Transport Equation
T	: Transmittance
USA	: United States of America
UV	: Ultraviolet
VIS	: Visible Spectrum

SYMBOLS

%	: Percent
\int	: Integral
$\cos(\theta)$: Cosinus of the angle of θ
n_1	: Refractive indices of first medium
n_2	: Refractive indices of second medium
μ'_s	: Reduced scattering coefficient
ϑ_1	: Speed of lights at first medium that light comes
ϑ_2	: Speed of lights at medium which refracts the light
θ_1	: Angle of incident light
θ_2	: Angle refracted light,
μ_s	: Scattering coefficient
$^{\circ}\text{C}$: Degree celcius
c	: Speed of light in medium
cm^2	: Square centimeter
g	: Anisotropy factor
$\text{k}\Omega$: Kilo Ohm
mW	: Milli Watt
n	: Refractive index
v	: Speed of light in vacuum
$p(\theta)$: Probability function of a scattered photon at the angle of θ
a	: Optical albedo
λ	: Wavelength

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OPTICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF COLLAGEN IN SOLUTION BY USING DOUBLE INTEGRATING SPHERE SYSTEM

SUMMARY

Optical systems and techniques are widely used in physics, biology and medicine as a diagnostic and therapeutic approach, as well as for characterizing optical properties of tissues. Today, light-based treatments and applications are very important applications to eliminate cancer and cancer-like diseases. It is very important not to damage the tissues while applying laser, and only interested area should be affected by the laser. Optical characterization studies should be conducted to optimize light effects and the literature in this field should be developed.

Collagen is the most abundant type of protein in mammals. For biomedical laser applications on tissues such as skin which is collagen-rich, it is important to know the optical properties of collagen before the application and to know how they change during the application in order to obtain successful results.

Optical properties of collagen in acidic solutions with different concentrations were estimated using inverse adding-doubling (IAD) method. Double integrating sphere system with a special sample heating apparatus and temperature control unit for screening the temperature were used to observe the effect of temperature change on optical properties of collagen. Temperature dependent optical properties of collagen solutions and concentration dependency of these optical properties were investigated in this study. The results showed that reflectance values were negatively correlated with temperature, and reflectance at higher acid concentrations showed lower correlation. Contrary to the reflectance values, the transmittance values were positively correlated with temperature, and the transmittance values at higher acid concentration showed a lower correlation. It was also found that the reduced scattering coefficients were negatively correlated with temperature and the absorption coefficients were positively correlated with temperature, but there was no significant change for different concentrations of acidic solutions. By using Monte Carlo simulation, the effect of optical property changes on light propagation through samples was demonstrated. Consequently, optical properties may vary with temperature and these variations should not be ignored for safer biomedical laser applications.

ÇİFT TOPLAYICI KÜRE SİSTEMİ KULLANILARAK ÇÖZELTİDEKİ KOLAJENİN OPTİK NİTELENDİRİLMESİ

ÖZET

Optik sistemler ve teknikler fizikte, biyolojide, tıpta tanı, tedavi yaklaşımı olarak ve ayrıca dokuların optik özelliklerinin nitelendirilmesi için yaygın olarak kullanılmaktadır. Günümüzde ışık temelli tedaviler ve uygulamalar, kanser ve kanser benzeri hastalıkları ortadan kaldırmak için çok önemli uygulamalardır.

Laser ile uygulama yapılırken dokulara zarar vermemek çok önemlidir ve laserden sadece ilgili bölge etkilenmelidir. Işık etkilerini optimize etmek için optik nitelendirme çalışmaları yapılmalı ve bu alandaki literatür geliştirilmelidir.

Laser uygulamalarında, termal etkiler dokuların optik özelliklerinde değişikliklere neden olabileceği gibi laser uygulamasının başarısını da etkileyebileceğinden, termal hasar da dikkate alınmalıdır. Bu nedenle laser uygulaması sırasındaki sıcaklık değişimleri dikkate alınarak dokuların optik özellikleri değerlendirilmelidir.

Optik özellikler denildiğinde temel olarak yansıma, geçirgenlik, soğurma ve indirgenmiş saçılma katsayıları akla gelmektedir. Yansıma, bir ortamdan yansıyan ışık yoğunluğunun ortama gelen ışık yoğunluğuna oranıdır. Geçirgenlik, bir ortamdan diğerine iletilen ışık yoğunluğunun ortama gelen ışık yoğunluğuna oranıdır. Soğurma, ışık-doku uygulamaları için çok önemli bir parametredir ve bir doku veya ortamdan geçerken ışık yoğunluğunun azalması olarak tanımlanır. Saçılma, elektromanyetik dalga yayılımının orijinal yönden bir veya daha fazla farklı yöne sapmasıdır. Saçılma katsayısı, mesafe başına saçılan fotonların oranı olarak tanımlanır.

Optik özelliklerin belirlenmesi için farklı yöntemler kullanılmaktadır. Bu yöntemler temel olarak Işınım Salınım Denkleminin (RTE) yaklaşık analitik çözümleri ve sayısal çözümlerine dayanmaktadır. Denklem sayısal çözümlerine yinelenmeli teknikler de denir. Bu çalışmada optik özelliklerin belirlenmesinde yinelenmeli tekniklerden olan çift toplayıcı küre sistemi kullanılmıştır. Bu teknikte doku ve numunelerin yansıma ve geçirgenlik değerleri ölçülür. Kürelerin iç duvarları (içi boş) yansıtma değeri yüksek malzemelerle kaplanmıştır. Numune iki küre arasına yerleştirilir. Işığın geçtiği birinci küre yansıma, ikinci küre ise geçirgenlik değerlerini bulmak için kullanılır. Işık ilk toplayıcı küreye ulaştığında, kürenin duvarlarından yansımaya başlar, dedektörler aynı anda ışık yoğunluğunun bir fonksiyonu olarak yansıma ve geçirgenlik değerlerini ölçer.

Ters ekleme-katlama (IAD) yöntemi, Scott Prahl ve diğerleri tarafından yansıma ve geçirgenlik ölçümlerinden dokuların veya ortamların absorpsiyon ve saçılma özelliklerini tahmin etmek için geliştirilmiştir. "Ters", optik özelliklerden yansıma ve geçirgenliği hesaplama sürecinin tersine çevrilmesi anlamına gelir; "Toplama-katlama", ışınım salınım denklemini çözmek için kullanılan yöntemi ifade eder.

Bu yinelemeli yöntemde, çeşitli optik özellikler tahmin edilir, yansıma ve geçirgenlik değerleri hesaplanır. Bu değerler ölçülen değerlerle karşılaştırılır. Değerler eşleşirlerse, bir numunenin optik özellikleri (soğurma, indirgenmiş saçılma katsayısı vb.) bulunur. Bu çalışmada optik özelliklerin değerlendirilmesinde çift toplayıcı küre sistemi ve ters ekleme-katlama yöntemi kullanılmıştır.

Doğada kolajen, farklı hayvan kaynaklarında bulunan en yaygın protein türüdür. Vücuttaki birçok dokuya yapısal destek sağlar. Yirmiden fazla tip olmasına rağmen, tip I, II ve III tek başına insan vücudundaki tüm kolajenin %80-90'ını oluşturur. Tip I deri, kemik, tendon, dentin ve bağ gibi yapılarda en sık görülen tiptir. Tüm kolajen türleri, üçlü sarmal yapı oluşturan polipeptit zincirlerinden oluşsa da, küçük bölümlerde farklılık gösterdikleri için farklı üç boyutlu şekillere katlanmalarına neden olabilir. Bu yapılar hidrojen bağları ve polipeptit çapraz bağları ile korunur. Denatürasyon sıcaklığında, molekülleri birbirine bağlayan bu hidrojen bağları ve polipeptit zincirleri koparak üçlü sarmalın açılmasına neden olur. Sonuç olarak, kolajen jelatin adı verilen homojen olmayan bir proteine dönüşür. Denatürasyon sıcaklığı dokudan dokuya değişir. Çok sayıda çalışma, kolajen veya kolajenden zengin dokuların sıcaklığa bağlı denatürasyon özelliklerini tanımlamaya odaklanmıştır. Kolajen denatürasyonunu inceleyen çalışmalar daha çok kolajenin yapısal değişikliklerini gözlemlemeye yönelik görüntüleme yöntemleri kullanmıştır. Denatürasyon sürecinin kolajenin optik özelliklerindeki değişimlerine odaklanan çalışma sayısı kısıtlıdır. Denatürasyon sürecinin optik açıdan değerlendirilmesi, laser kullanılan uygulamalarda (a) sıcaklık derecesi, (b) ısıya maruz kalma süresi, (c) kolajen içerikli doku mühendisliği ürünleri üretilirken ısıl işlemlerin ayarlanması ve (d) uygulanan laserin güç, dalgaboyu ve uygulama süresi gibi özelliklerin belirlenmesinde rehberlik eder.

Cilt gibi kolajen bakımından zengin dokulara biyomedikal laser uygulamaları yapılırken, kolajenin optik özelliklerinin uygulamadan önce ve uygulama sırasında nasıl değiştiğinin bilinmesi başarılı sonuçların alınabilmesi için önemlidir. Bu çalışmanın birincil amacı, 532 nm ve 635 nm'de laserler kullanarak (a) farklı konsantrasyonlarda ve (b) farklı sıcaklıklarda kolajen çözeltilerinin optik özelliklerindeki değişiklikleri gözlemlemektir. İkincil amaç, optik özellikleri değerlendirirken kolajen tendonları çözmek için kullanılan asetik asit çözeltisinin optimal konsantrasyonunu belirlemektir.

Bu tez çalışmasında kolajenin asidik çözeltilerdeki optik özellikleri (yansıma, geçirgenlik, soğurma ve indirgenmiş saçılma katsayıları), sıcaklık değişimi ile karakterize edilmiştir. Ayrıca 4 farklı konsantrasyonda asidik çözelti kullanılarak bu özelliklerin konsantrasyon bağımlılığı gösterilmiştir.

Çift toplayıcı küreli optik sistem kullanılarak sıcaklığa bağlı optik özelliklerin değerlendirilmesine yönelik çalışmalar için üç grup olduğu söylenebilir. Birinci grup, özel yapım numune tutucuya sıcak su pompalayan su banyolu numune tutucu tasarımını içerir. Bu tasarımlarla ilgili sınırlamalar, (a) sıcaklık değişiminin hızlı yapılamaması ve (b) sistemin su kontrollü kısım içermesi nedeniyle optik bir sistemin yanında elverişsiz olmasıdır. İkinci grup sıcaklık kontrollü kutular içerir. Kapalı bir kutuda optik sistem kurmak zordur, bu zorluğun yanı sıra dedektörler ve küreler numunelerle birlikte ısıtılmak zorundadır. Bu ısı dedektörlerde gürültünün artmasına neden olabilir ve kaplama malzemesinin sıcaklık hassasiyeti ölçümlerde bazı problemlere neden olabilir. Son grup ise, optik sistem tasarımlarında ısıtıcı

plakaların kullanımını içerir. Bununla birlikte, ısıtıcı plakaların boyut kısıtlamaları vardır, çünkü sinyal kaybı yaşanmaması amacıyla iki toplayıcı küre arasında için numune koymak için çok az boşluk kalmalıdır. Dolayısıyla bu tasarımın da toplayıcı kürelerle kullanımı zordur. Bu çalışmada kullanılan Peltier ısıtıcı ile tasarlanan numune tutucuda hareketli parça ve sıvı bulunmamaktadır. Bu numune tutucu ayrıca hızlı sıcaklık değişimi sağlar.

Sıcaklık değişiminin kolajenin optik özellikleri üzerindeki etkisini gözlemlemek için, bir ısıtma-soğutma mekanizmalı numune tutucu aparat ve Arduino kontrollü sıcaklık kontrol ünitesi ile çift-toplayıcı-kürelili optik sistem kullanıldı. Sıcaklık değişimi Arduino programının 'Serial Port' ekranından gerçek zamanlı olarak izlendi. Öncelikle sıcaklığa bağlı olarak, PicoScope isimli PC osiloskop cihazının yazılımı aracılığıyla kolajen çözeltisinin yansımaya ve geçirgenlik değerleri bulundu. Ardından bulunan değerler tezin giriş bölümünde anlatıldığı şekilde normalize edildi. IAD yöntemi kullanılarak, soğurma ve indirgenmiş saçılma katsayıları hesaplandı. Sonuçlar, yansımaya değerlerinin sıcaklıkla negatif korelasyona sahip olduğunu ve daha yüksek asit konsantrasyonlarındaki yansımaya daha düşük korelasyon sergilediğini gösterdi. Yansımaya değerlerinin aksine, geçirgenlik değerlerinin sıcaklıkla pozitif korelasyona sahip olduğunu ve daha yüksek asit konsantrasyonundaki geçirgenlik değerlerinin daha düşük korelasyon gösterdi. Ayrıca, indirgenmiş saçılma katsayılarının sıcaklıkla negatif korelasyona sahip olduğu ve soğurma katsayılarının sıcaklıkla pozitif korelasyona sahip olduğu, ancak asidik çözeltilerin farklı konsantrasyonları için önemli bir değişiklik olmadığı bulundu.

Sıcaklık değişiminin ışık yayılımı üzerindeki etkisini gözlemlemek için, daha önce elde edilen soğurma ve indirgenmiş saçılma katsayıları kullanılarak bir Monte Carlo simülasyonu yapıldı. Işık akışında değişimler gözlemlendi ve sıcaklığa bağlı olarak örneğin optik özelliklerindeki değişimlerin ışığın örnek içindeki akış ve yayılımını değiştirebileceğini gösterildi.

Sonuç olarak, optik özellikler sıcaklıkla değişebilir ve daha güvenli biyomedikal laser uygulamaları için bu değişiklikler göz ardı edilmemelidir.

1. INTRODUCTION

Optical systems and techniques are widely used in physics, biology, medicine as a diagnostic and therapeutic approach, as well as for characterizing optical properties of tissues. Today, light-based therapies and applications are very important applications to eliminate cancer and cancer-like diseases.

When dealing with a laser, it is really important to apply laser without any damage on tissues and only the region of interest should be affected by the laser. To optimize light effects, optical characterization studies should be performed and literature about optical characterization should be improved.

For laser applications, thermal damage should also be taken into consideration because thermal effects may cause changes in optical properties of tissues as well as affect the success of laser application. For this reason, optical properties of tissues are evaluated by considering temperature changes during laser application.

Collagen is the most abundant protein constituent among soft tissues and hard tissues of mammals. Use of collagen has increased in many areas, and the high amount of collagen in tissues, such as, skin and nails, has led to examination of collagen in this study. In fact, when dealing with skin-like applications of lasers, knowledge on optical properties of collagen and on the effects of temperature change on optical properties due to structural deformation at high temperatures should be available for success. Besides, collagen is a useful biomaterial with different forms for tissue engineering applications, such as, surface modification of biomaterials. It is important to know collagen's optical, mechanical, and physical properties for such applications. With this in mind, collagenous tissues and lasers in the visible region of light are selected for this study.

1.1 Light-Tissue Interactions

Firstly, light-tissue/matter interactions and what happens when light is delivered to tissues should be known to understand optical property measurement systems. Therefore, some optical definitions will be given and optical interactions will be explained in this section.

Figure 1.1 : Schematics of light propagation through tissues.

1.1.1 Refractive index

Refractive index is dependent on wavelength and determines the reflectivity and refractivity of the matter. It is the ratio of speed of light in vacuum to that in the medium.

$$n = \frac{c}{\vartheta} \quad (1.1)$$

where, n is the refractive index, c and ϑ represent speed of light in medium and vacuum, respectively. c equals to 299,792,458 m/s.

1.1.2 Reflection, refraction and transmission

Reflection is described as the throwing back of a light by a reflective surface which is the physical boundary between two materials with different refractive indices, like tissue and air (Figure 1.1). Reflectance is the proportion of reflected light intensity to incident light intensity. If the irregularities on the surface are insignificant compared to wavelength, this reflection is named specular reflection. On the other hand, if these irregularities are in the range of wavelengths or greater, diffuse reflection comes into play. Diffuse reflection occurs in almost all tissues due to roughness of the surface.

Reflection and refraction are actually related to Fresnel's Law. Refraction happens if the reflective surface separates two media which have different refractive indices and seems as a change in direction of the incident light. This is caused by a variation in the speed of light. The basic relationship is explained by Snell's Law.

$$\frac{\sin\theta_1}{\sin\theta_2} = \frac{v_1}{v_2} = \frac{n_2}{n_1} \quad (1.2)$$

where θ_1 and θ_2 are the angles of incident and refracted light, v_1 and v_2 are the speed of light in the first medium that light comes from, and the medium which refracts the light, n_1 and n_2 are the refractive indices of first and second medium, respectively (Figure 1.1).

Transmission is defined as permission of light to pass to the other side of interface between two media. Non-absorbed and non-reflected light is transmitted and measured on other side of the interface. Transmittance is the ratio of transmitted light intensity to incident light intensity.

If all light is reflected and there is no transmission, this type of reflection is called total internal reflection. In addition, if there is no reflection, the angle of that situation is named Brewster's angle [1].

1.1.3 Absorption

Absorption is a crucial parameter for light-tissue applications and it is defined as the attenuation of light intensity when passing through a tissue or a medium. Absorption mainly depends on wavelength. Absorbance is the ratio of absorbed light to incident light. If a medium absorbs all light and there is no transmitted light, this type of medium is called ‘opaque’, and if the medium allows transmission of all incident light, this type of medium is called ‘transparent’ (Figure 1.1) [1].

1.1.4 Scattering

Scattering is deviation of electromagnetic wave propagation from the original direction into one or more different directions. Scattering coefficient is defined as the ratio of photons scattered per distance. Scattering can be divided into elastic and inelastic scattering. If the energy of scattering waves changes, this case is called inelastic scattering, e.g. Brillouin and Raman. If the energy of waves is unchanged after scattering, this case is called elastic scattering. It occurs due to differences in refractive indices and inhomogeneities in the tissue. There are different types of elastic scattering. In Rayleigh scattering, size of inhomogeneities in tissues are smaller than the wavelength, and in Mie scattering, these inhomogeneities are about the size of wavelength [1].

1.1.5 Anisotropy factor and turbid media

Every scattering causes deflection from the original direction at an angle θ . Anisotropy factor is defined as average of deflection and mean value of $\cos(\theta)$ and can be calculated by following equation:

$$g = \frac{\int_{4\pi} p(\theta) \cos(\theta) d\omega}{\int_{4\pi} \cos(\theta) d\omega} \quad (1.3)$$

where g is the anisotropy factor and $p(\theta)$ is the probability function of a scattered photon at the angle of θ . It can take values from -1 to 1. The positive values of g refer to forward scattering and negative values of g refer to the back scattering [1].

The reduced scattering coefficient is also critical parameter and can be calculated as:

$$\mu'_s = (1 - g)\mu_s \quad (1.4)$$

where μ'_s is the reduced scattering coefficient, g is the anisotropy factor and μ_s is the scattering coefficient.

Turbid medium is a medium in which both absorption and scattering events occur. Optical albedo is a characteristic property and can be calculated as:

$$a = \frac{\mu_s}{\mu_s + \mu_a} \quad (1.5)$$

where a is the optical albedo, μ_s is the reduced scattering coefficient and μ_a is the absorption coefficient.

1.2 Calculation Methods for Optical Properties

There are several techniques to measure optical parameters such as transmittance, reflectance and scattered light intensity. It is difficult to measure absorption only, so it is calculated by subtracting reflected, transmitted and scattered intensity of light from incident light intensity [1].

Techniques for calculating optical properties of tissues are as follows :

- approximate analytic solutions and
- numerical solutions of Radiative Transport Equation (RTE)[1-3].

RTE explains behaviour of light in tissue or medium. Analytic solutions are called non-iterative solutions and due to complex solution of RTE, analytic solutions are done under some assumptions. These methods have some limitations, such that, less accuracy, time consumption and having different case for difference in thickness of the tissue. For instance, Beer's law or first order scattering can only be applied to very thin tissue sections and does not include multiple scattering. This method is only suitable for thin tissue sections with a low scattering coefficient. Another direct method is the Kubelka-Munk theory which suffers from accuracy. Time-resolved spectroscopy and radial reflectance spectroscopy containing diffusion approximation is a poor approach when the optical albedo is nearly 0.5. Numerical solutions of RTE are also called iterative techniques. One of the most used numerical or iterative

approach is Monte Carlo Method which is based on a random photon scattering within the tissue. It has good accuracy if the number of photons is large, but suffers from computation time. The other iterative technique is based on integrating sphere and inverse-adding-doubling, which will be explained in the next sections.

1.3 Double-Integrating-Sphere Method

Reflectance and transmittance values of tissues and samples are measured preferably with the double integrating sphere method. The interior walls of the spheres (hollow cavity) are covered with materials that have high reflectivity value. The sample is placed between the two spheres. The first sphere through which the light passes is used to find the reflectance and the second sphere is used to find the transmittance values. The port width through which the light will pass must be equal in both spheres. In this study, LabSphere 4P-GPS-033-SL double integrating sphere system was used. In this system, the inner surface of the spheres is covered with a material called spectralon. This material has fairly flat properties in Ultraviolet (UV), Visible Spectrum (VIS) and Near Infrared Spectrum (NIRS). At the same time, it is Lambertian. When the light reaches the first integrating sphere, it begins to reflect from the walls of the integrating sphere, detectors simultaneously measure reflectance and transmittance values as a function of light intensity.

Any light which impinges on the inner surface via multiple scattering reflections is distributed evenly. The system can be considered as a diffuser that removes spatial information while maintaining power. Usually, an integrating sphere has a baffle inside, close to the sample region, which prevents the first reflection from falling onto the detector, and only evenly scattered diffuse light is collected by the detector.

The biggest advantage of the Double Integrating Sphere Method is that diffuse reflectance and total transmittance measurements are performed simultaneously [4, 5]. Total transmittance consists of diffuse transmittance and collimated transmittance. Also, total reflectance is equal to the sum of diffuse and specular reflectance. Furthermore, the value of μ_a and the value of the reduced scattering coefficient $\mu'_s = (1 - g)\mu_s$ could be calculated from the two measurements by inverse adding doubling method that will be explained in the next section. If the value of g should be calculated, collimated transmittance should be to be measured.

Collimated transmittance can be measured by placing a third detector on the exit port of second integrating sphere.

Figure 1.2 : Necessary measurements for calculating MR and MT if two integrating spheres are used (This image is taken from IAD program manual).

1.4 Inverse Adding Doubling

The inverse adding-doubling (IAD) method was developed to estimate absorption and scattering properties of tissues or turbid media from reflection and transmission measurements by Scott Prahl et al. [6]. The main advantages of this method according to other methods are better accuracy and flexibility in modeling turbid samples with intermediate albedos, mismatched boundary conditions, and anisotropic scattering. Yet, this method is completely numerical which might be a disadvantage.

“inverse” implies that reversal of the process of calculating reflectance and transmittance from optical properties; “adding-doubling” refers to the method used to solve the radiative transport equation. In this iterative method, several optical properties are guessed and reflection and transmission values are calculated. These values are compared with the measured values. If they match, optical properties of a sample are found [7].

The IAD program has some parameters that can be changed according to different experimental set-ups. First step of IAD is defining these parameters:

Table 1.1 : Parameters which is needed for IAD header file.

• Thickness of sample
• Thickness of slides
• Diameter of illumination beam
• Reflectance of calibration standard
• Number of spheres
• Reflection and Transmission Sphere Diameters
• Reflection and Transmission Sphere Sample Port Diameters
• Reflection and Transmission Sphere Entrance Port Diameters
• Reflection and Transmission Sphere Detector Port Diameters
• Reflectivity of the sphere walls
• Index of refraction of sample
• Index of refraction of slides

Other steps are calculation of the reflection and transmission coefficients, comparison of calculations and measurements, repeating the same process until the estimated values come closer to measurements, respectively.

In this study, the value of μ_α and μ'_s were estimated by using normalized reflectance and transmittance values which were found with double integrating sphere technique. The measurements were done by irradiating the sample between integrating sphere with laser light. The diffuse reflectance was measured in the first integrating sphere by collecting the reflected and back-scattered light whilst the total transmittance was measured in the second sphere by integrating the transmitted and forward scattered light.

The value of μ_α and μ'_s were estimated by inverse adding doubling algorithm with the use of normalized reflectance and normalized transmittance values. Measured reflectance and transmittance values can not be used directly in this algorithm. They should be normalized with the incident light [8].

The calculations needed for normalized reflectance:

$$M_R = \frac{(R_2(r_s^{direct}, r_s, t_s^{direct}, t_s) - R_2(0,0,0,0))}{(R_2(r_{std}, r_{std}, 0, 0) - R_2(0,0,0,0))} \quad (1.6)$$

And the calculations needed for normalized transmittance:

$$M_T = \frac{(T_2(r_s^{direct}, r_s, t_s^{direct}, t_s) - T_2(0,0,0,0))}{(T_2(0, 0, 1, 1) - T_2(0,0,0,0))} \quad (1.7)$$

where r_{std} is the value of the reflectance standard, $R_2(r_s^{direct}, r_s, t_s^{direct}, t_s)$ is the diffuse reflectance measured value of the sample, $R_2(0,0,0,0)$ is the background noise of the reflectance sphere, $R_2(r_{std}, r_{std}, 0, 0)$ is the maximum diffuse reflectance value with the reflectance standard, $T_2(r_s^{direct}, r_s, t_s^{direct}, t_s)$ is the total transmittance measurement, $(T_2(0, 0, 1, 1))$ is the maximum transmittance value and $T_2(0,0,0,0)$ is the background noise of the transmittance sphere with the sample. The necessary measurements to calculate M_R and M_T are shown in Figure 1.2.

1.5 Optical Characterizations of Tissues and Samples via Double-Integrating-Sphere Systems

The application of double integrating spheres in biomedical optics, such as, the measurement of optical properties (absorption and scattering coefficients) of biological tissues, plays a vital role in understanding the interaction of light with tissues in photodiagnosis and phototherapy. Specifically, optical properties are indicators of microstructure and biochemical composition of tissues, and can be used to distinguish healthy and pathological tissues (such as cancer, skin burns, etc.). Additionally, optical properties of tissues are essential for understanding and optimizing light-based treatment modalities (such as photodynamic therapy, photoablation etc.)[9].

The aim of this study was to determine temperature effects on optical properties of collagen in acetic acid solutions. Studies in the literature about measurements of temperature related optical properties suffer from poor or inadequate experimental methods. Most of the published studies to find effects of thermal damage on optical properties are inadequate to estimate the relationship between temperature and optical properties of tissues. In these studies, generally tissue samples were thrown into hot water bath or heated by a hot plate and all measurements were taken at room temperature, quite unrealistic than the normal situation.

A two-port plastic tissue holder that was attached to a water bath was designed by Agah et al.[10]. A hot saline solution was pumped into the tissue holder to heat the tissue. They discovered that when temperature rose, the reduced scattering coefficient increased and absorption increased.

Laufer et al. studied the temperature dependency of optical characteristics of human dermis and subdermis by taking optical measurements in a neonatal incubator [11]. The measurements were carried out at temperatures ranging from 25 °C to 40 °C. They determined that as the temperature rose, the normalized scattering coefficient increased for the dermis and decreased for the subdermis. Both tissue samples did not show a considerable difference in absorption coefficient.

To assess the optical property changes of ex vivo rat prostate due to heating, Skinner et al. devised a metallic sample holder method [12]. By flowing constant temperature

water through the sample holder, the sample was heated. The researchers discovered that the reduced scattering and absorption had changed.

By sandwiching cartilage tissues between aluminum plates, Basu et al. constructed a sample holder[13]. The tissue was then cooked on a hotplate with a single spherical. They discovered that as temperature rose, diffusely transmitted light decreased, remained almost constant, and then increased. Diffusely reflected light, on the other hand, showed the opposite behavior.

Kim et al. studied the effects of temperature-dependent optical properties of porcine skin by investigating fluence rate and temperature during low-level laser therapy (LLLT) [14]. They measured reflectance and transmittance by using double-integrating sphere method inside a styrofoam box with a heating gun to alter the temperature. The study showed that the reduced scattering coefficient of porcine skin decreased as the temperature of skin rose from 26 °C to 40 °C.

When high temperatures are applied to tissues, their physical, mechanical and optical properties can change. For this reason, it is necessary to investigate the relation between optical properties and temperature change.

1.6 Collagen

In nature, collagen is the most abundant type of protein found in different animal tissues. It provides structural support to many tissues in the body. Although there are more than twenty types, types I, II and III alone account for 80-90% of all collagen in the human body [15, 16]. Type I is the most common type in structures, such as, skin, bone, tendon, dentine, and ligament. Although all collagen types are composed of polypeptide chains that form a triple helix structure, they differ in small sections that can cause them to fold into different three-dimensional shapes. These structures are maintained by hydrogen bonds and polypeptide crosslinks. At the temperature of denaturation, these hydrogen bonds and polypeptide chains break and cause unfolding of the triple helix structure. As a result, the collagen turns into an inhomogeneous protein called gelatin [17]. The denaturation temperature varies from tissue to tissue [15]. A large number of studies have focused on defining temperature-dependent properties (mechanical, electrical and optical properties) of collagen or collagen-rich tissue [15, 18-20].

(a)

(b)

Figure 1.3 : Denaturation of collagen structure by temperature. (a) Collagen triple helix structure(straight). (b) Denaturated collagen triple helix structure.

One of the biggest issues encountered in biomedical applications is the toxic effect of the material used. Collagen is a natural material source, and the fact, that collagen has not shown a significant toxic effect in the studies so far, has caused collagen to have a widespread use in biomedical applications. Also, collagen has a high tensile strength between 1.4 and 24.6 MPa and it is able to wear high strength without plastic deformation [15]. The appropriate properties of collagen makes it a good biomaterial. In order to make it suitable for use, collagen must be regenerated in different forms (film, membrane, fiber). Since collagen is found in the form of fiber in the structure of the extracellular matrix, its production in this form is especially important for its use in areas, such as, biomedical and tissue engineering [16].

Collagen is very good biomaterial for tissue engineering. Collagen solution is preferred for the surface modification when dealing with cell adhesion. Some studies have used collagen as a modifier for improving cell attachment to the surface of the flasks, scaffolds or plates in tissue engineering. These studies have found that collagen's porous properties make it suitable for cell growth and useful surface modifier for better cell attachment [21-23]. Thus, collagen is also useful as scaffold for tissue growth [24, 25].

Besides tissue engineering applications of collagen, increase or decrease in the density of collagen in different tissues can be a sign of anomaly. For example, some researchers found that collagen density in breast tissues is associated with breast density and, accordingly, with breast cancer risk [26, 27]. Skin is also collagen-rich, thus, to optimize light applications to skin, the number and findings of optimization studies for different tissues are important.

In the present work presented in this thesis, because of the significance of collagen to mammals, collagen was chosen to determine temperature dependency of optical properties. Temperature effect is important while working with lasers because laser photothermal effects might cause a rise in temperature in tissue samples or solutions. When considering heat denaturation process, characterization of collagen was investigated using several different techniques at different temperatures, such as, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy [28], scanning electron microscopy [29], atomic force microscopy [30], differential scanning calorimetry [28], optical coherence tomography [31], and mueller matrix polarimetry [32].

There are some studies about collagen absorption spectrum for potential diagnostic applications and tissue characterization. One of them [33] is an optical characterization study about breast composition. It is found that the amount of collagen can be evaluated by time-resolved spectroscopy as a non-invasive method and it provides correlation with breast density. The other is also optical characterization of collagen over 500-1700 nm range by using time-domain diffuse optics and it is compared with other characterization studies of collagen in literature [34]. That study discussed that several tissue components contribute to absorption properties of collagen-rich bone tissue location and proposed possible bone diagnostics. Shcheslavskiy et al. used Hyper-Rayleigh scattering to measure nonlinear optical properties of collagen in acetic acid solution [35]. It was found that as the concentration of collagen in the solution increased, the first rate of hyperpolarization unexpectedly decreased. Measurement of circular dichroism absorption showed that the helical conformation remains stable and the change in non-linear optical properties of the collagen molecule was probably due to the formation of some supramolecular structures of collagen in solution.

Studies about heat dependent optical characterization of collagen is limited in literature. Derman et al. [32] investigated temperature dependence of optical properties of collagen in acidic and natural solutions by using Mueller Matrix Polarimetry and Principal Component Analysis. They found the denaturation temperature of collagen as 33.38 ± 2.78 °C and 36.83 ± 2.43 °C for acidic and natural solutions, respectively. Sun et al. [36] used fluorescence spectroscopy as a low-cost method to determine thermal stability of collagen mimic peptides and they found that this method is appropriate for triple helix systems.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Sample Preparation

Preparing Collagen from Rat Tail Tendon

The abundance of collagen in the structure of the tendons and the fact that the majority of the rat tail is composed of tendons made this source an ideal source for the extraction of collagen. Therefore, the majority of recent studies have focused on this source. Rajan et al. (2007) created a protocol for collagen extraction from rat tail in their study. Preparations were mostly carried out with minor modifications based on this protocol [37].

Rat tail tendons were obtained from Wistar Rat ($n = 6$, ~ 12 months old, weight: 400–420 g), which were taken from and isolated at the Central Vivarium of Bogazici University.

Figure 2.1 : Extraction of collagen from rat-tail. (a) cutting tail from a rat. (b) removal of skin by a scalpel and pulling tendons with a forcep. (c) putting tendons into 1X PBS solution and pre-processing. (d) stirring acidic-tendon solution to make gel on magnet. (e) putting collagenous gel into dialysis tube against distilled water.

First, the tails that were provided frozen were thawed in 1X PBS solution. Then a scratch was made on the hard skin of the tail with the help of a scalpel. The skins rising from this scratch edge were cut with the help of surgical scissors. The tendons were pulled one by one with the help of a fine forceps and filled into 1X PBS solution in the same way. Tendon extracting process and removed tendons are shown in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2 : Extraction of tendons from rat tail.

Tendons were pre-processed in accordance with the protocol followed. The tendons were washed with distilled water and then kept in acetone for 5 minutes and isopropyl alcohol for 5 minutes, respectively. It was washed again with distilled water and 1 g of tendons was placed in 0.02 M, 100 ml acetic acid. (0.115 ml of acetic acid -99.885 ml of distilled water) The solution, which was stirred with a 1300 rpm magnetic stirrer for 3 days, was gelled.

In order to remove the acid in the solution, dialysis was performed in a dialysis tube for 3 days against distilled water.

The solution obtained after dialysis was frozen at -85 °C for 1 night and then lyophilized for 48 hours. At the end of the lyophilization process, the water molecules were completely removed and the powdered collagen was successfully obtained.

Figure 2.3 : Lyophilization of tendons. (a) dialysis of collagen solution against distilled water. (b) putting acid-free solution into beaker. (c) freezing acid-free solution at $-85\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 night. (d) lyophilization for 48 hours. (e) powdered collagen.

After lyophilization, 0.02 M, 0.05 M, 0.075 M and 0.1 M acetic acid solutions were prepared and pH of each solutions were measured with pH meter. 1 g of lyophilized collagen was added to each 100 ml of acetic acid solutions. Each collagen solutions were stirred with a 1300 rpm magnetic stirrer for 3 days in cold for preventing denaturation of collagens.

Table 2.1 : pH of Prepared Acetic Acid Solutions.

Molarity of Acetic Acid Solutions	pH of Acetic Acid Solutions
0.02 M	2.71
0.05 M	2.57
0.075 M	2.45
0.1 M	2.29

2.2 Optical Property Measurement System Design with Double-Integrating-Sphere

In this study, double-integrating-sphere system was used with chopper controller, lock-in amplifier and PC oscilloscope as seen in Figure 6. As the light source 532 nm laser was used. The beam size was controlled by lenses and diaphragms. A double-integrating sphere (4P-GPS-033-SL, LabSphere) was used to measure the reflected and transmitted light detected by silicon detectors denoted as R and T (SDA-050-P-RTA-CX, Lab-Sphere), respectively. The detector is working in the visible range of light (380 nm-780 nm). For the elimination of other wavelengths' signal by modulating incoming light and extraction of the detected modulated signals from the detectors, chopper duo (SR540, Stanford Research Systems) and lock-in amplifiers (SR510, Stanford Research Systems) were used. The chopper rotates to block applied light periodically. There was also chopper controller to control frequency or period. Lock-in amplifiers use a technique known as phase-sensitive sensing to separate the component of the signal at a given reference frequency and phase. Noise signals at frequencies other than the reference frequency are rejected and do not affect the measurement. Signals were taken by PC oscilloscope (PicoScope 2000 series) and its software.

Figure 2.4 : Experimental set-up with double-integrating-sphere.

2.2.1 Temperature control part

For the temperature controller part of the study, the sample holder which was designed by Ercan Kara in his PhD thesis were used [4]. Some modifications were made on the sample holder control part that will be explained in this section of the study.

Figure 2.5 : Temperature control circuit of the sample holder.

Figure 2.6 : Top view drawing of sample holder [4].

Figure 2.7 : The picture of sample holder [4].

In this study, DS18B20 temperature sensor was used with a $10\text{ k}\Omega$ resistor and it directly put into the sample. This temperature sensor has better sensitivity according to LM35 temperature sensor. That's why DS18B20 was chosen as a temperature sensor. 8 channel relay module was used as an electrical switch to control peltier's heating and cooling mechanisms. And Arduino Uno was used as a microcontroller of the circuit (Figure 2.5). Temperature change monitored via Arduino's serial port screen.

2.2.2 Sample cuvette designs

Liquid samples are used in this system so, it was needed to put samples in a sealed cuvette. Normally, quartz and glass cuvettes are a little bit expensive in our country. So a cost-effective 3D printable cuvette was printed with Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS) filament and it was arranged as 3 mm sample thickness. After printing, glass slides were cut as a 25 mm:25 mm square and slides are glued to the cuvette as seen in Figure 7.A. But this design was used without a sample holder heating system. It is not appropriate for the use of a temperature sensor. So, another design as seen in Figure 7.B was created with 10 mm sample thickness to put a temperature sensor inside the cuvette. But there was another problem about sticking the glass to the design because of our acidic solution. This design was not appropriate due to leakage of the solution. Therefore, it couldn't be used with a sample holder. Finally, polystyrene spectrophotometer cuvettes were chosen as a sample cuvette with 10 mm sample thickness and a temperature sensor was put inside of the cuvette during the measurement.

Figure 2.8 : 3D Design of the Sample cuvette. (a) First design which is designed for heating without sample holder. (b) Second design which is designed for the use with sample holder and temperature sensor.

2.2.3 Experimental setup

The system design and experimental setup will be explained in this section. A double-integrating sphere system was used to measure the amount of reflected and transmitted light by the sample. Explained control unit was used with the sample holder design and the measurements were done with the screening of temperature change via serial port of Arduino simultaneously. The laser source had a wavelength

of 532 nm with 100 mW/cm² output power. Table 2.2 shows the experimental setup and sample geometry parameters.

Table 2.2 : Experimental Setup and Sample Parameters.

Parameters	Value
Wavelength (nm)	532
Thickness of sample (mm)	10
Diameter of illumination beam (mm)	4,12
Top Slide Thickness (mm)	1,0
Bottom Slide Thickness (mm)	1,0
Reflectance of the calibration standard	0,99
Number of spheres used during each measurement	2
R-Sphere Diameter (mm)	83,8
R-Sample Port Diameter (mm)	12,70
R-Entrance Port Diameter (mm)	12,70
R-Detector Port Diameter (mm)	12,70
R-Reflectance of the sphere wall	0,992
T-Sphere Diameter (mm)	83,80
T-Sample Port Diameter (mm)	12,70
T-Entrance Port Diameter (mm)	25,70
T-Detector Port Diameter (mm)	12,70
T-Reflectance of the sphere wall	0,992

3. RESULTS

Experimental procedure includes heating up the samples from 10 °C to 50 °C and measuring normalized reflectance and transmittance. Reduced scattering and absorption coefficient values were computed by the IAD program. Input parameters of the IAD were the normalized reflectance and total transmittance, refractive index of the sample, anisotropy factor as well as double-integrating-sphere system setup and sample parameters. The refractive index of collagen is determined by the formula:

$$n_{col}(\lambda) = 1.426 + \frac{19476}{\lambda^2[nm]} - \frac{1131066900}{\lambda^4[nm]} \quad (3.1)$$

where $n_{col}(\lambda)$ is the refractive index of collagen and λ is the wavelength of the light source [38]. The refractive index was calculated as 1.48.

Anisotropy factor (g) of rat tail tendon was found as 0.95 at a wavelength of 535 nm according to a study about wavelength dependency of second harmonic generation of collagen [31]. So, g was taken as 0.95 in this study due to close relationship with this finding of the study.

Measurements were carried out with the experimental setup discussed earlier. Signals were detected by silicon detectors attached on double integrating spheres. After detecting incoming light signal with PicoScope software, signals were normalized by the formulae 1.6 and 1.7. Subsequently, these normalized reflectance and transmittance values were used in IAD calculations for estimation of absorption and reduced scattering coefficients.

3.1 Normalized Reflectance and Transmittance

The values of normalized diffuse reflectance and transmittance were measured in one-degree increments. Heating up each sample during measurements from 10 °C to 50 °C took around 30 minutes. The normalized diffuse reflectance and transmittance values are represented by black dots. The blue and claret red line show the fourth-order polynomial fitted values of normalized diffuse reflectance and transmittance, respectively. Reflectance showed negative correlation and the transmittance showed positive correlation with the increase in temperature. Correlation coefficients of the plots for each concentration values were indicated in Table 3.1. It may be conjectured that the structural variations of the collagen samples due to temperature change have an effect on the reflection and transmission characteristics.

Figure 3.1 : Change of normalized reflectance and transmittance of collagen in 0.02 M acetic acid solution with temperature.

Figure 3.2 : Change of normalized reflectance and transmittance of collagen in 0.05 M acetic acid solution with temperature.

Figure 3.3 : Change of normalized reflectance and transmittance of collagen in 0.075 M acetic acid solution with temperature.

Figure 3.4 : Change of normalized reflectance and transmittance of collagen in 0.1 M acetic acid solution with temperature.

Table 3.1 : Correlation coefficients of normalized reflectance and transmittance with temperature graphs for different concentration values.

Concentration Value	Correlation Coefficients	
	Reflectance	Transmittance
0.02 M	-0,89429	0,802174
0.05 M	-0,93077	0,800629
0.075 M	-0,93237	0,738242882
0.1 M	-0,9358	0,41983

3.2 Absorption and Reduced Scattering Coefficients

The values of absorption and reduced scattering coefficients were calculated by using IAD and plotted as a function of temperature. The absorption and reduced scattering coefficients represented by black dots. The green and orange line show the fifth-order polynomial fitted values of absorption and reduced scattering coefficients, respectively. The absorption coefficients showed positive correlation and reduced scattering coefficients showed negative correlation with the increase in temperature. Correlation coefficients of the plots for each concentration values were indicated in Table 3.2.

Figure 3.5 : Change of absorption and reduced scattering coefficients of collagen in 0.02 M acetic acid solution with temperature.

Figure 3.6 : Change of absorption and reduced scattering coefficients of collagen in 0.05 M acetic acid solution with temperature.

Figure 3.7 : Change of absorption and reduced scattering coefficients of collagen in 0.075 M acetic acid solution with temperature.

Figure 3.8 : Change of absorption and reduced scattering coefficients of collagen in 0.1 M acetic acid solution with temperature.

Table 3.2 : Correlation coefficients of absorption and scattering with temperature graphs for different concentration values.

Concentration Value	Correlation Coefficients	
	Absorption	Reduced Scattering
0.02 M	0,602533955	-0,916553006
0.05 M	0,89254146	-0,902644496
0.075 M	0,911501747	-0,921398825
0.1 M	0,882366287	-0,913297784

3.3 Monte Carlo Simulations for the Fluence Rate

Figure 3.9 : Monte Carlo simulation results for 0.02M collagen-acetic acid solution (i) at 21 °C, (ii) at 50 °C and (iii) difference in the fluence rates between 21 °C and 50 °C.

To observe the effect of temperature on light propagation, a Monte Carlo simulation was performed using the absorption and reduced scattering coefficients previously found at 21°C and 50°C for 0.02M collagen-acetic acid solution. The fluence rate at these two temperatures and the difference in logarithmic scale are shown in Figure 3.9. Positive colors indicate that the flow rate at 21°C is higher than at 50°C. Changes in fluence rate were observed, showing that optical property changes as a function of temperature can change the fluence rate and light propagation within the tissue.

4. DISCUSSION

The primary objectives of this study were to observe changes in optical properties of collagen solutions ;

(a) at different concentrations and

(b) at different temperatures, using lasers at 532 nm and 635 nm.

The secondary objective was to determine optimal concentration of acetic acid solutions used to solve collagen tendons when estimating optical properties.

Our literature review on optical properties at 532 nm indicated that 532 nm wavelength is more appropriate for skin like tissues than 635 nm, because 532 nm has lower penetration than 635 nm. Besides, the 635 nm laser in Biophotonics Lab at Boğaziçi University provided by Professor GÜLSOY had very unstable output power and measurements were not consistent. Another 635 nm laser provided by Professor FERHANOĞLU from ElectroOptical Devices Lab at İstanbul Technical University had very low output power (5.2 mW/cm^2) and thus measurements were excessively noisy.

A serious limitation confronted was the limited amount of collagen solutions due to the limited number of harvested rat tails. Therefore, measurements were carried out mostly at 532 nm and results with 635 nm were not included in this thesis.

Besides of these limitations mentioned above, it was clearly seen that when the acid concentration increased, fluidity of collagen solutions increased. And also, increase in temperature led to increase in fluidity of collagen solutions.

According to literature search, it was known that high acidic concentration causes deformations of the structure of collagen [32]. In this study, the results of the measurements made with 0.1M acetic acid-collagen solution showed some differences compared to other concentrations. These differences are shown comparatively in the graphs below.

Figure 4.1 : Comparison of the change in normalized reflectance values with temperature for different concentrations of collagen solutions.

As seen in Figure 4.1, graphs of normalized reflectance for 0.05 M and 0.075 M collagen solutions have similar tendency as temperature increases. Normalized reflectance for 0.02 M collagen solution is higher than other concentrations in general. Finally, normalized reflectance values for 0.1 M collagen solution have slightly different tendency. This difference may be due to the high acid concentration. It can be said that reflectance of collagen solutions decreases with increase in temperature for the range of 10 °C and 50 °C.

Figure 4.2 : Comparison of the change in normalized transmittance values with temperature for different concentrations of collagen solutions.

As observed in Figure 4.2, graphs of normalized transmittance values for concentrations of 0.02 M, 0.05 M and 0.075 M show an increase above 30 °C and they have similar tendency. When these three curves are compared, normalized transmittance values for concentrations of 0.05 M and 0.075 M are very close but values for 0.05 M is higher than 0.075 M and also 0.02 M. Normalized transmittance values for concentration of 0.1 M have different tendency from others such as decreasing above 38 °C and have high transmittance. This difference may also be due to high acid concentration. High acid in the solution might cause deformation of collagen samples, difference in the structure of collagen can cause such differences in optical properties.

Figure 4.3 : Comparison of the change in absorption coefficients with temperature for different concentrations of collagen solutions.

In Figure 4.3, absorption coefficients of 0.05 M collagen solution and 0.075 M collagen solution show very similar tendency but absorption coefficients of 0.02 M collagen solution reach its maximum around 35 °C and decrease above this point. However, absorption coefficients of 0.1 M collagen solution are higher than the rest. It can be discussed that the concentration differences have influence on the absorption of the samples. High acidity of solution causes deformation of collagen structure, this deformation may in return cause an increase in absorption.

Figure 4.4 : Comparison of the change in reduced scattering coefficients with temperature for different concentrations of collagen solutions.

In Figure 4.4, reduced scattering coefficients of 0.02 M collagen solution are the highest. 0.05 M and 0.075 M collagen solutions have almost similar coefficients but above 17 °C, scattering coefficients of 0.05 M collagen solution are higher than 0.075 M. In general, optical properties of 0.1 M collagen solution show different tendency with temperature. It can be clearly said that reduced scattering coefficients decrease with the increase in temperature in the range of 10 °C and 50 °C. Also, the highest acidic collagen solution has the lowest scattering coefficients. It is probably due to deformation of collagen structure caused by high acidity. The triple helix structure of collagen can break with high acid and the absence of triple helix may prevent scattering of light. It can be also said that optical properties of collagen solutions are concentration and temperature dependent.

According to findings of this study, it can be said that optimal concentrations of acetic acid solutions used to solve collagen tendons are 0.05M and 0.075M acetic acid solutions when estimating optical properties due to close relationship between these two concentrations and their relations with increase in temperature are more consistent according to others.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

In this study optical properties (reflectance, transmittance, absorption and reduced scattering coefficients) of collagen in acidic solutions were characterized as a function of temperature change by using an optical measurement system with a heating-cooling mechanism that was used in reference 4 [4]. Also, concentration dependency of these properties was shown by using 4 different concentrations of acidic solution. The main focus of the studies about denaturation of collagen is to show structural change [15, 28-30]. There are limited number of studies on temperature dependent optical properties of collagen and these studies are mainly about absorption spectrum of collagen[33-35]. Our objective was to investigate effects of thermal denaturation on different optical properties of collagen.

There were three groups for the studies on measuring temperature dependent optical properties by using double integrating sphere. The first group includes sample holder design with water bath that pumped hot water to a custom-made sample holder [10-12]. Limitations with these designs are (a) difficulty about the temperature change quickly and (b) being inconvenient next to an optical system because the system contains a water-controlled part. The second one has temperature-controlled boxes [11-14]. It is difficult to build optical system in a closed box. This difficulty aside, detectors and spheres are heated together with samples. This heat may lead to an increase in noise at detectors and temperature sensitivity of the integrating sphere coating material may cause some problems in measurements. The last group contains the use of hot plates with optical system design[13]. However, the hot plates have size constraints because there must be very little space between the two integrating spheres to accommodate the sample and to avoid loss of signal. Therefore, this design is also difficult to use with integrating spheres. There are no moving parts and liquids in the sample holder designed with Peltier used in this study. This sample holder also provides fast temperature change.

This study could be expanded to other types of samples and tissues for a wide range of temperatures and different types of light sources with different wavelengths to

make a reference for optical applications, such as, photodynamic therapy, biostimulation, photothermal therapy, ablation and so forth, and possible diagnostics purposes. For example, in optical applications, such as, photodynamic therapy to cancerous tissues, the change of optical properties of tissues can be examined before, during, and after application. In this way, the effects of the application on the structure of the tissue can be observed.

In addition, the study can be extended by using different solvents other than acid. A wider scan can be performed using different types of collagen and different temperature ranges.

The optical properties of collagen as scaffold and also how collagen's surface modification efficiency change by photobiomodulation can be examined.

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